

1 **FMR1 and DTNA: neurodegeneration-associated machinery possess functions in lineage**
2 **commitment in the human embryo.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We report here that FMR1 and
9 DTNA, neurodegeneration-associated machinery, possess functions in lineage commitment in the human
10 embryo.

11 Citations

12 1. Gerhardt, J., McCarter, K., Deshpande, M., Romanski, P., Stratopoulou, C.A., Zaninovic, N. and
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